

Supplementary Material for Pheromones to Policies: RL for Biological Swarms

1 Cross-learning equivalence derivation

1.1 Case 1: Site i is Chosen

Assume site i is chosen at time t . Then

$$\tau_i(t+1) = \rho \tau_i(t) + Q, \quad \tau_k(t+1) = \rho \tau_k(t) \quad (\forall k \neq i). \quad (1)$$

Only $\tau_i(t)$ receives an increment of Q , while all other pheromone levels $\tau_k(t)$ for $k \neq i$ are solely subject to evaporation by the factor ρ . Therefore, when normalizing to compute $P_i(t+1)$, the additional pheromone Q contributes only to the chosen site's term, resulting in $Q A_i$ in the denominator. Hence the probability of choosing site i at time $t+1$ becomes:

$$P_i(t+1) = \frac{[\rho \tau_i(t) + Q] A_i}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_i}. \quad (2)$$

We rewrite $\tau_i(t)$ in terms of $P_i(t)$ by noting

$$\tau_i(t) = \frac{P_i(t)}{A_i} \left[\sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j \right]. \quad (3)$$

Substitute into (2):

$$\begin{aligned} P_i(t+1) &= \frac{\rho \tau_i(t) A_i + Q A_i}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_i} \\ &= \frac{\rho \left[\frac{P_i(t)}{A_i} \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j \right] A_i + Q A_i}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_i} \\ &= \frac{\rho P_i(t) \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_i}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_i}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Define

$$r = \frac{Q A_i}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_i}. \quad (5)$$

Rewriting to highlight the increment in $P_i(t)$ yields

$$P_i(t+1) = P_i(t) + r [1 - P_i(t)]. \quad (6)$$

Thus, if site i is chosen, $P_i(t)$ is incremented by a factor proportional to $[1 - P_i(t)]$.

1.2 Case 2: Site i is Not Chosen

If site i is not chosen at time t , then there is no new pheromone added to $\tau_i(t)$, so

$$\tau_i(t+1) = \rho \tau_i(t). \quad (7)$$

Meanwhile, exactly one other site (say $k \neq i$) is chosen and thus gets reinforced. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_k(t+1) &= \rho \tau_k(t) + Q, \\ \text{and for all others } j \neq \{i, k\} : \\ \tau_j(t+1) &= \rho \tau_j(t). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

We can now convert these $\tau_i(t+1)$ values to updated probabilities by normalizing over the sum of all pheromone \times attractiveness terms:

$$P_i(t+1) = \frac{\rho \tau_i(t) A_i}{\sum_{j=1}^M [\rho \tau_j(t) + \Delta_j] A_j}, \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta_j = Q$ if j was chosen, and 0 otherwise. Since exactly one site k is chosen,

$$\sum_{j=1}^M [\rho \tau_j(t) + \Delta_j] A_j = \rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_k. \quad (10)$$

Hence

$$P_i(t+1) = \frac{\rho \tau_i(t) A_i}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_k}. \quad (11)$$

Expressing $\tau_i(t)$ in terms of $P_i(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} P_i(t) &= \frac{\tau_i(t) A_i}{\sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j} \\ \implies \tau_i(t) &= \frac{P_i(t)}{A_i} \left[\sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Substitute back to get

$$\begin{aligned} P_i(t+1) &= \frac{\rho \left[\frac{P_i(t)}{A_i} \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j \right] A_i}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_k} \\ &= P_i(t) \frac{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_k}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Factor out $P_i(t)$ and rewrite the fraction:

$$P_i(t+1) = P_i(t) \left(1 - \frac{Q A_k}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_k} \right). \quad (14)$$

Define

$$r = \frac{Q A_k}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + Q A_k}. \quad (15)$$

Then the update law becomes

$$P_i(t+1) = P_i(t) - r P_i(t), \tag{16}$$

showing that if site i is not chosen, its probability $P_i(t)$ decreases by a fraction r proportional to $P_i(t)$ itself.